

AN ANALYSIS OF WRITING SKILL APPROACHES OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS: A TWO DIMENSIONAL STUDY FROM DISTRICT NAUSHAHRO FEROZE

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Abstract

English writing skills remain challenging task for students as they are not equipped enough to cope with the emerging trends in writing. This research analyses the approaches, perspectives and practices of teachers with respective writing skills. It is observed that teachers adopt product approach while teaching English writing skills whereas use of Process approach has not gained their cognizance. The methodology adopted in this research is Quantitative descriptive method and the survey questionnaire is used to collect the data. Purposive sampling technique is employed while the target population is eight secondary Govt schools of Naushahro Feroze. The sample comprises of 104 students and 32 teachers equally selected from the population of eight schools of three Talukas out of five Talukas District Naushahro Feroze. The Data analysis was conducted on Statistical package for social sciences by applying statistical tools of percentages, frequencies, Standard deviation Mean and Pearson's Correlation. The findings of the study reveals that teachers in Govt. schools at tenth Grade do not adopt process approach of writing skills. When the data was collected and analyzed from teachers it was found that Teachers have knowledge about process approach but they do not practice process approach in the class rooms. This study recommended that process teaching approach may be embedded while developing curriculum and teachers should incorporate the process approach teaching methods while inculcating English writing skills. Doing so, students can enhance their creativity and critical thinking and rote learning will be discouraged.

INTRODUCTION

People communicate in English language worldwide and share with one another the information, knowledge and culture, so it has become very challenging for the teachers teaching English as a second language to prepare the students who can display the competency and command of English language communication

skills in their personality (Krivosheeva, 2020). The speedy development of English language practice across the world has demanded competence from learners in all four skills of language – reading, writing, listening and speaking but several studies confess that L2 learners have to deal with countless

problems in learning this foreign language (Siddiqui, 2020).

Known as one of the most spoken languages worldwide, English has definitely been given serious attention as second language (ESL) or foreign language (EFL) learning in many educational institutions around the globe (Selvaraj & Aziz, 2019; Ugun & Aziz, 2020). This is because English is used in many domains such as for international interaction, education, business and trade. One is deemed proficient in the language if they could master all four skills, namely reading, listening, speaking and writing. However, writing skill is perceived as the most difficult one among those four (e.g. Alabere & Shapii, 2019; Chandran et al., 2019; Rashtchi et al., 2019; Selvaraj & Aziz, 2019; Suryana & Iskandar, 2015; Ugun & Aziz, 2020).

The importance and popularity of English Language learning in Pakistan is on rise and it is a compulsory subject in schools and colleges with a prime purpose of enabling students to have mastery on English language communication skills (ELCS) that include reading, writing, listening and speaking (Khan, 2015). Writing in comparison to three other skills is considered to be more powerful one because through this skill, learners express their thoughts and beliefs (Nair & Wider, 2020).

In the production of language; writing is a significant skill and its importance is multiplied when it comes to the writing skill of English language which is widely used for the international negotiation of knowledge, so the performance of learner with reference to the development of language is directly related to the improvement in the writing skills (Fareed & Bilal, 2016; Lashari, Umrani & Buriro, 2021).

Learning writing skill can be a useful thing for the writer as such skill besides supporting the writer to improve grammatical structures, idioms, mechanics and vocabulary also enhances the learners' adventurous attitude towards language, their involvement with the language effort for better expression of ideas (Naibaho, 2016). Most people consider the learning of writing difficult as compared to listening, speaking and reading because it is a process for creating ideas from the

learners' knowledge so that such ideas may be written (Yulianti, 2019).

The basic thing that makes writing a hard nut to crack is that writer does not know where and how to start from and where and how to end the writing (Barras, 2008). Writing is not only putting down words or sentences on paper instantly, but it is a process of thinking (Nurfaidah, 2018). In such a process of thinking; writers need to relate lots of fact and to compare the fact or they need to think of what facts need to be written, so writing is aligned with the topics of writing (Guzman, 2019). Out of four language skills, writing is the one found difficult by the students (Samsudin, 2016). What makes writing more difficult in the higher secondary schools is the formal orientation of characteristics of the writing skill (Bayat, 2014). Students seem to be between the devil and the deep sea where on the one hand they are directed to correct the form and usage of the writing skill and on the other hand they are strictly directed to focus on logical ordering, removal of irrelevancy, justification of ideas and precision (Klein, 1999).

The purpose of teaching writing is that it is a basic component which engages students in professional, social, community and civic activities (Kellog, 2008). It helps students in transferring their thoughts and ideas to the readers (Johnson, 1999). It gives an element of encouragement to the students to remain absorbed with the text in order to deeper their understanding of the content (Hedge, 2001). The three major aims of teaching writing skill to students according to (Cassany, 1999) are teaching of realistic compositions so that students may have variety of topics to write, teaching of communicative and functional writing and the teaching of writing for the improvement of competence.

There are five major groups of L₂ learners among grown-ups and teenagers whose learning of English writing varies purposefully from one another (Bernhart, 1991). In teenagers, first is the group of those children who wish to be triumphant in their school and college. Second is the group of those who are deeply involved in learning writing with a purpose of enhancing their

education. In grown-ups, third is the group of immigrants to a new country where learning of English writing is the main source of their survival in the workplace. Fourth group is of those adults who are studying abroad in any university where the needs of learning English writing skill almost double (Lashari & Umrani, 2023). Fifth is a group of those adults who learn English writing skills owing to their personal interest, bright career or educational purpose. This study is focusing on the learning of writing skill of teenagers in school and college.

Writing whether done in the mother tongue or any second language is undoubtedly a great challenge (Maarof & Murat, 2013). It works as a powerful tool for communication, a great source for self-expression and valuable mechanism for learning (Graham, 2008). As a communication tool, it removes the time and distance between people, as a useful source, it helps in creating an imaginary description about people, places and things, convincing people about different viewpoints and as a mechanism for learning, it helps in exploring, organizing and refining the ideas.

Writing well is an art and the learning of this art is requirement for students because their success in the schools and colleges and the field of work depends upon it (Graham & Perin, 2007).

The students are said to be disadvantageous in the college if they struggle with writing skill, because it is the primary source by which they are assessed in their content knowledge by the teachers (Graham & Perin, 2007). With poor knowledge of writing, students of the college are not equipped to meet the challenges of university life (Program, 2004). In the same way, such writers are immensely at a disadvantage in the work place because both government and private employers give an indication that writing skills are affecting the decisions related to the hiring and promotion of the employees to my).

In the most advanced technological world of today, a big number of the jobs in our society require mastery of writing skills for preparing reports, memos and letters and in this connection writing skill must be taught to the students so that they may not struggle during ongoing job period

(Harmer, 2008). One cannot through orally done activities achieve the mastery of skills of the rich built vocabulary, good command of grammatical structures and mechanics and versatility of writing in terms of using idiomatic language including phrasal verbs, so one has to make continuous practice to become the most skillful and efficient writer and in this regard the most consolidated way of ameliorating and refining one's writing skill is to write simple essays so that one can grow one's creative skills and widening the horizons of thinking (Jabbarova. A, 2020).

It is also vital to realistic goals and professional activities (Smith. C, 2020). Not only this; it is also methods of research, expressiveness, thinking, publication, role negotiation, identity formation and social integrations (Dastageer, 2019). Moreover, it constitutes the core of assessment in language education and an essential part of undergraduate courses in Pakistan and all over the world (Manzoor, Azhar & Malik, 2020).

Literature Review

In Pakistan, despite having 49% of English Language users, the writing skills of the students are not much desirable (Fareed, Ashraf, & Bilal, 2016). The issues faced by the students in English writing specifically include inability in syntax (Younas. Zeb & Aziz, 2019). Selection of content (Bakeer, 2018). generation, organization, expansion of ideas (Farhana & Yasmin, 2018) and lack of vocabulary (Dar & Khan, 2015). These issues are owing to certain factors which are identified and categorized into particular areas by the previous studies (Muhammad & Masum, 2018), for instance, unsuccessfulness of the teachers for teaching the writing skill (Abbas, Faiz, 2017), unsuccessful teaching approaches (Abbas, Aashique, 2018) and lack of interest of teachers in teaching writing skill (Aftab. & Rabbani, 2018). According to Channa & Panezai (2019) the mismatched teaching strategy also causes the lack of confidence in the students because it is not aligned with the learning styles of the students and their cultural backgrounds. Another study in the literature highly criticizes those teachers by tagging them with the word incompetent that they in place of enhancing creative skills among the students

insist them to rote memorization and exam-related language production (Zahid& Hooley, 2019).

Previous studies on product and process teaching approaches for teaching writing skill in English language

Regarding effectiveness of process teaching approach, there are many studies being done in different contexts. One study by Kamal Aziz (2015) is done in the context of Iraq which presents the effect of Scaffolding on the writing ability of ESL students through process teaching approach. Researcher used the technique of scaffolding that comes in one of the five stages of the process teaching approach and solely focused on this particular element to improve the writing skill of learners. The five stages of the process that this study contained were prewriting, drafting, revising, editing and publishing. The results of this study concluded that the use of process approach with reference to the teacher's use of technique of scaffolding in teaching writing skill enhanced the students' capability of writing skill by providing necessary practice and skills required by learners to compose an error free and purposeful piece of writing.

Another study by Ruegg (2015) is conducted in a Japanese context regarding the effect of written feedback by the teacher in a process teaching approach on the ESL learners' writing ability. Researcher's spotlight in this study was fixed on the feedback by teacher in the process teaching approach. This research study concluded that the students learning English in the universities improve in their writing skills by leaps and bounds when they are given written feedback time and again on their composed drafts.

According to the findings of a study done in the context of Labella district Pakistan by (Muhammad ,2018), the teaching of English writing skill in Pakistan is similar to the teaching of other subjects like Pakistan studies and general science. Moreover, the conclusion of this study further clarifies that the teaching approach in Pakistan for teaching writing skill is teacher-centered and the learners are neither provided with any chance of improving language skills nor involved in any classroom practices where they can

build their skills of creative and critical thinking. This study holds few things responsible for such condition of students with reference to the poor writing skill; such as, lack of capacity building programs or courses for language teachers, overcrowded classrooms, teachers' workload, poor infrastructure, examination system and inefficient monitoring system. The study further recommends that teachers teaching English language need to be trained before assigning any class for teaching the English language.

As per a study done in the context of Karachi by (Saniya 2018), the major problems that the students in Pakistan face in ESL writing are lack of pre-writing activities, learners' less command over vocabulary, grammar, spelling and punctuation, lengthy syllabus and limited time. The study concludes that students in Pakistan encounter numerous problems in writing skill just because of lack of ideas to start a writing activity, limited vocabulary and missing of written feedback from the teachers. This study suggests that the teachers need to be trained in adopting a particular teaching approach while teaching writing so that students may be motivated to write and build their vocabulary.

One study at secondary level schools in Pakistan by (Faisal,2020) regarding an analysis of English Language Teaching and Learning Process concludes that grammar translation method (GTM) is the commonly popular method of teaching English Language writing skill among the ESL teachers in Pakistan and out of four skills, the maximum focus is given on speaking skill whereas, the least on Writing skill. This study further suggests that instead of translating national or regional language into English, teachers had better engage students in brainstorming their ideas first and let them write later. In doing so, teachers must be given trainings on suitable teaching approach for teaching particular type of writing.

There are many other previous studies focused on process teaching approach and its impact on overall writing ability. There is hardly any work available in the existing literature whose central idea is revolving the teachers own perspectives about writing and writing practices, it is therefore, the gap found by the researcher and intended to

conduct quantitative descriptive research to analyze the relationship between English language teachers perspectives and practices about English

writing skills in two dimensions i.e Teacher’s own knowledge of English writing approaches and their practices by surveying from their students.

HAYES 1981 MODEL V/S HAYES 2012 MODEL

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Research Method and Research Design

The researcher intends to adopt descriptive survey research design in this study, because according to (Fraenkel, et al, 2011), the purpose of this research design is to describe existing relationships, held beliefs, evident effects and developing trends. The population of this study is the English language teachers and their students in secondary schools Boys & Girls equally of three Talkas out of five Talkas of district NaushahroFeroze. Through Purposive sampling the researcher selected the respondents from the census of population which includes total eight secondary schools in the whole of district NaushahroFeroze. Total number of respondents is nearly 32 Tenth Grade teachers and 104 students. The researcher used Quantitative by method descriptive research design in nature because it is apprehensive with the situation that exists, a practice that prevails, the attitude that is detained,

the practice which is going on, and trains that are emerging (Gay,1976). It helps to acquire sufficient information about perspectives and practices of English Language Teachers in two dimensions. It can also generalize to the large- scale on the whole population.

Procedure of Data Collection

Quantitative research is the systematic empirical exploration of the observable phenomena through statistical of observable phenomena through statistical and quantifiable techniques. The main rationale of quantitative research is to build up mathematical computable techniques or hypotheses linked to a special process to develop the understanding. The whole procedure of measurement is in-depth in quantitative research because it gives the basic relation and link between empirical observation and mathematical expression of quantitative relationship. The

quantitative measurement is standardized and it is expressed numerically, this data is used numerical forms such as percentage, quartile, frequency mean, mode, standard deviation. These entire things mentioned above are quantifiable calculations and computations. The methodology adopted in this research is Quantitative descriptive method and the survey questionnaire is used to collect the data. Purposive sampling technique is employed while the target population is eight secondary Govt. schools of Naushahro Feroze. The sample comprises of 104 students and 32 teachers equally selected from the population of eight schools of District Naushahro Feroze. The Data analysis was conducted on SPSS by applying statistical tools of percentages, frequencies, Standard Deviation and Mean. The research method employed in this study is quantitative. Quantitative descriptive research method is used to analyze the relationships. For collecting data of the study, Instrument will be in the form of close

ended questionnaires, one for knowing perspectives of teachers regarding the nature of writing, importance of writing and the approach of writing and other for knowing the practices of these teachers from their students. The participants of the study are the male and female English Language Teachers from 8 different schools for girls and boys from 4 different cities of the district Naushahro Feroze. The other sample of participants is the students of English Language Teachers of tenth Grade from same school. The data was analyzed with the help of static calculations. The researcher assumed that the numbers and digits and figures give unbiased results.

Data Analysis, Findings And Discussion Pearson's Correlation coefficient Results and analysis

RQ: 1 Is there any relationship between approach of teachers and English writing skill approaches?

RQ: 2 Is there any relationship between practices of teachers and English Writing Skill approaches?

Descriptive Statistics

Standard Deviation

N = 32 0.47

N = 104 0.32

Analysis:

1. Teachers' Approaches:

Mean (3.586): The mean value of 3.586 indicates the average score for teachers' approaches. This value is on whatever scale was used for measuring teachers' approaches.

Standard Deviation (0.4737): The standard deviation measures the variability or dispersion of the scores around the mean. A standard deviation of 0.4737 suggests that the teachers' approaches scores are fairly consistent, with most scores falling within approximately 0.4737 units of the mean.

2. Students' Writing Practices:

Mean (1.3286):

The mean value of 1.3286 indicates the average score for students' writing practices. This value reflects the central tendency of the students' writing practices scores.

Standard Deviation (0.3197):

The standard deviation of 0.3197 indicates the variability in students' writing practices scores. It suggests that the scores are relatively clustered around the mean, with most scores falling within approximately 0.3197 units of the mean.

3. Sample Sizes:

Teachers' Approaches (N = 32):

The sample size of 32 for teachers' approaches is relatively small, which might affect the reliability and generalizability of the findings.

Students' Writing Practices (N = 104):

The sample size of 104 for students' writing practices is more substantial, providing a more reliable estimate of the mean and standard deviation for this variable.

Conclusion:

Teachers' Approaches:

The average score is 3.586 with a standard deviation of 0.4737, indicating that the scores are fairly consistent.

The relatively small sample size (N = 32) means that these results should be interpreted with caution, as they might not be representative of a larger population.

Students' Writing Practices:

The average score is 1.3286 with a standard deviation of 0.3197, suggesting that the scores are relatively close to the mean.

The larger sample size (N = 104) provides more confidence in these descriptive statistics,

making them more reliable and likely to be representative of the larger student population.

In conclusion, the descriptive statistics provide an overview of the central tendency and variability of teachers' approaches and students' writing practices. The teachers' approaches show a moderate level of consistency among the scores, while the students' writing practices have a relatively low mean with moderate variability. Further analysis, including inferential statistics, would be necessary to explore any potential relationships or differences between these variables in more depth

Correlations

	Teachers' Approaches	Students' Approaches
Teachers' Approaches		
Pearson Correlation	1	.134
Sig. (2-tailed)	—	.466
N	32	32
Students' Approaches		
Pearson Correlation	.134	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.466	—
N	32	104

Interpretation and Analysis

1. Pearson Correlation Coefficient :

The Pearson correlation coefficient between teachers' approaches and students' approaches is 0.134. This value indicates a very weak positive correlation between the two variables.

A correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1. Values close to 1 or -1 indicate strong correlations, while values near 0 indicate weak or no correlation.

2. Significance (Sig. 2-tailed):

The p-value associated with the Pearson correlation is 0.466. In statistical analysis, a p-value less than 0.05 is typically considered statistically significant.

Here, the p-value is 0.466, which is much higher than 0.05, indicating that the correlation is not statistically significant. This means that we cannot conclude there is a meaningful relationship between teachers' and students' approaches based on this data.

3. Sample Size (N):

The sample size for teachers' approaches is 32, and for students' approaches, it is 104.

A larger sample size generally provides more reliable results. However, in this case, despite a sample size of 104 for students, the correlation remains weak and non-significant.

Conclusion:

The analysis of the Pearson correlation between teachers' approaches and students' approaches shows a very weak positive correlation of 0.134. However, this correlation is not statistically significant, as indicated by the p-value of 0.466.

Given the sample sizes of 32 for teachers and 104 for students, the data does not provide strong evidence to support a meaningful relationship between the approaches of teachers and students. The high p-value suggests that the observed correlation could likely be due to random chance rather than a true underlying relationship.

In conclusion, based on the provided data, there is no significant correlation between teachers' and students' approaches. Therefore, any educational strategies or policies aimed at linking teachers' and students' approaches should be re-evaluated or supplemented

with additional data and analysis to confirm any potential relationships.

Findings

This research aims at finding the relationship between the writing skills approaches and English teachers' approaches and practices. This two dimensional study investigates the English language teachers own understanding of writing skills by putting up the statements in likert scale. The first ten statements in the questionnaire attempt to investigate the teachers perspectives about nature of writing. It is evident from data analysis that majority of the teachers have their orientation more towards the product based statements and they lack awareness of process approach. They are more focused on final product of writing rather than the process of writing itself. The statements from 11 to 16 attempt find the perspectives of teachers about what is important about product approach and process approach. It is found from date analysis of these six statements that teachers have more knowledge about the important factors involved in product approach and they have minute knowledge of important factors involved in process approach. The last fourteen statements in the questionnaire are about what teachers themselves intend to practice in class. The approach they adopt in conducting class. It is evident in data analysis of last fourteen statements that teachers adopt product approach in teaching writing skills during their day to day teaching. Since it is evident from item wise data analysis that teachers adopt product approach in teaching writing skills, it is further proved from Pearson's Co efficient results that there is positive relation between executing product approach and teachers own preference of adopting product approach in teaching learning process within the class. The practices of teachers were further corroborated by raising questions from their students. The ten questions comprising amalgamation of product approach and process approach were posed to the students. The results show the percentages and frequencies towards the practice of product approach and process approach remains out of their knowledge or preference. As the majority of questions were about to investigate the practice of product based teaching approach as a result Pearson's Coorelation Coefficient reflects negative relationship as the

teachers practice process approach less and more they practice Product approach.

Discussion

This chapter is based on Data Analysis, Findings and discussion

It is widely observed that teachers in public sector frequently adopt Grammar Translation Method and other traditional ways of teaching English. Such methods and ways are embedded with product approach and notions involved in it. The perspectives and practices of teachers in public sector schools is due to either unawareness about the new approaches or they intend to follow traditional ways. Keeping in view both the scenarios, teacher has a pivotal role to play in first place he must equip himself with process approach and notions embedded in it and in second place as a change agent must shun away from traditional ways of teaching English writing skills. Incorporating collaborative and cyclic approach of writing will certainly bring about change of creativity and innovation in the writing craft of the students.

The inability of teachers to apply classroom-based examples to increase students' cognitive capacity will contribute to poor writing skills (Moses et al., 2019). Teachers who use a mental process lens allow students to write without restriction. Setting a time limit will enable students to brainstorm and write down their ideas. However, some students can still correct errors in their writing and use visual planners to help organize their ideas (El Soufi & See 2019). The stimuli to generate thoughts are an advantage, but some students may struggle to recall their thoughts promptly. Environmental distractions can cause a lack of focus, Writing is an important study skill for all students. A fast "To Write is a method in which students are given a topic, issue, or idea to write about and a time limit. Students should register for the entire period, regardless of errors. Students could use this method. Preparing a topic helps students think in a specific direction and supports their writing. This quick method may confuse some students (Hodges & Tracey, 2017). Graphic organisers can also be used to improve writing patterns. It can use writing instructional strategies (Inaltekin & Goksu, 2019). Students could have used a mind map or timeline to generate ideas. This will help students create more

ideas for writing if they lack the visual sense and knowledge to extract pictures from mind maps.

HakimihShahroki (2018) in his study on impact of process and product approach on Iranian EFL learners has recommended process approach teaching for improving the writing ability among students. The study of Timothy (2012) suggested Process Approach to be an effective in terms of overall performance of students in essay writing.

There are some other studies which conclude process approach better than product approach. However, in all such studies which support Process approach over product; there are contextual differences. Such as, the study of Iranian writer supporting process approach is done on the EFL learners unlike this study which is conducted on the students of ESL. Some studies favoring process approach are conducted on the university students which are also in contrast to this study because it is done on the students of secondary education. One study by kamal Aziz (2015) is done in the context of Iraq which presents the huge positive effect of Scaffolding on the writing ability of ESL students through process teaching approach but this process teaching approach unlike the one used in this study is highly advanced and lengthy in terms of stages. It was based on five stages ranging from prewriting to the publishing of final draft by the EFL students of second year in the college.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the findings of this study that teachers do not have ample knowledge about teaching of English writing skills through process based approach. Teachers avoid teaching writing skills in some cases writing skills are not deemed as an important component of teaching English Language. Teachers assume teaching writing skills can be sufficed by providing certain samples of writing so that students may memorize.

In some cases teachers even do not adopt product approach in true sense. They do not even emphasize final product achieved through controlled process on the contrary model write ups are provided for mere rote learning. As a result, important domain of English Language at secondary level does not get inculcated and students are deprived of becoming effective and creative writers.

Many English Language Teachers have failed to produce creative and effective writers. English writing skills remain challenging task for students as they are not equipped enough to cope with the emerging trends in writing. This research analyses the approaches, perspectives and practices of teachers. It is observed that teachers adopt product approach while teaching English writing skills whereas use of Process approach has not gained their cognizance. The findings of the study reveals that Teachers in Govt schools at tenth Grade do not adopt process approach of writing skills when the data was collected and analyzed from teachers and they do not practice process approach when the data collected from students was analyzed.

The benefits offered by process approach to make the minds of secondary students creative and generative of ideas can be accessible to students when teachers incorporate in their teaching methodology various stages of process based approach of teaching writing skills. According to Hyland (2017), the three components of Process Teaching Approach like Written feedback, autonomy to write and collective engagement in a writing activity help students to improve their writing skill. Hu & Yu (2017) in their study regarding collective engagement of students in a writing task in a process teaching approach demonstrate that learners get maximum benefit from collective engagement while working in the groups. They learn by paying careful attention to one another and incorporate the constructive comments received through peer interaction. As students sit together for performing a writing task, they do not worry about grammatical structures and the particular vocabulary to be used, so this easiness during writing makes students skilled writers (Berninger, 2018). Moreover, the written feedback to the students according to Samsudin (2017) encourages students when they see in the written feedback that their assessor is not only pointing out their weak areas but also suggesting them what to do instead. One study by Lee (2016) on exploring the impact of written feedback on the essay writing suggests that teacher's written feedback under the process teaching approach is proved to enhance the writing development of the students. This feedback is constructive and contains the highlighted weaknesses and strengths of the learners which ultimately help them identify their problems and

mistakes in their composed piece of text and how to correct them to make their draft worth readable in the next attempt. The study of Kamal Aziz (2015) concludes that in process teaching approach, teachers' role is to act like a facilitator and to create a classroom environment conducive to make students autonomous writers. In other words, this approach helps students to figure out their weak areas in writing skill and get opportunity of working on their weaknesses and improve them.

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